

White paper: Introducing Lprobes[®] and XLprobes[®] technology for Atomic Force Microscopy

1) Context and previous state-of-the-art

Success and development of the Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) from its invention[1] has been based on the availability of probes that integrate a micro-mechanical compliant structure to a tip with nanoscale apex. The association of such probes with the optical beam deflection technique[2] has proven simple and successful for developing many AFM modes. In the 1990's, clean room microfabrication processes starting with silicon wafers were developed to obtain probes that can be produced in high volumes with an affordable probe unitary cost [3],[4, 5]. These processes fabricate the tips out of the wafer plane (Z), leading to the geometry shown in FIG. 1 (a). The cone angles as well as tip shapes result mostly from interplay with an initial mask and a wet etching step, where silicon dense planes that offer low etch rates will enable the tip cone slope. With this approach the tip cannot easily be upscaled above 15 μm because the wafer would become strongly non-planar, which is a limitation for the process integration. Moreover, extending the tip length would imply a large cone basis and a high mass, which lowers the frequency and could alter the first vibrating flexural mode.

2) New AFM probe technology based on advanced MEMS processing

To overcome these limitations and keep the batch process advantages in term of accuracy, cost, yield, and to provide higher performances with lower cost, Vmicro is introducing a new probe family where tip lengths can be designed from several microns to above one hundred microns. These probes have a typical shape described in FIG. 1 (b). They are based on modern Micro-Electro-Mechanical-Systems (MEMS) clean room technology that keeps the essence of silicon processing. One main difference compared to previous fab techniques is that we define the probe in the wafer (X,Y) plane instead of out-of-plane (Z). This requires mastering specific etching sequences and novel process integration schemes, while it enables much higher lengths and unlocks new designs.

FIG. 1: (a) typical tip shape obtained by previously known technologies of AFM probes production. Increase of tips lengths and aspect ratios is locked by the technology consisting in etching the tip out of the wafer plane, which would lead to high mass. (b) Vmicro in plane technology enables high tip lengths and high aspect ratios while keeping the concept of batch fabrication on wafers for volume production.

FIG. 2: (a) **Lprobe**[®] series based on patented technology developed by Vmicro in plane processing. These probes improve by a factor of 3 the tip length, by a factor of 2 the cone angle.

(b) **XLprobe**[®] series pushes the lengths to 110 μm a record for batch processed probes. The unprecedented shape enables low mass, safe flexural vibration modes, enabling operation with all the commercial AFM imaging modes.

FIG. 2 presents two AFM probes that have been obtained by clean room processing using Vmicro in plane manufacturing technology. (a) shows the Lprobe[®] series that offers a 30 μm tip and a native top view of the tip for very accurate landing when the AFM user has located a zone of interest. (b) shows XLprobe[®] that pushes the lengths even more, reaching a 110 μm record value. We can achieve new augmented aspect ratios where increasing the tip length will come with a limited increase in mass, thus preserving vibration frequencies. Lprobes[®] are available with different stiffnesses, tip coating, reflex coatings, and benefits from all the sharpening techniques previously known in the probe industry. In the following sections, this paper reviews several AFM use cases where this technology has an interesting potential to improve imaging performance.

3) Topography imaging using higher tip lengths

On a variety of samples such as unpolished natural materials, metallurgical surfaces, biological specimens, when using a standard tip (8-15 μm), only the most protruding areas of the sample can be imaged. The AFM scientist must take care not to engage in a region where the cantilever could touch the surface before the tip. Using a long tip as in FIG. 3 (b) greatly increases the number of samples that are compatible with AFM.

FIG. 3: Importance of the tip length for imaging with an AFM. (a) Using a small tip limits the cantilever clearance. (b) longer tip enables to address a wider range of samples. Note that the range of AFM Z-piezo ceramics imposes a limitation of the features that can be imaged. Whatever this range is, a long tip will unlock the AFM head approach and thus enable to locally image the topography.

FIG. 4: Importance of aspect ratio and half cone angle. (b) Vmicro tips offers a lower cone angle and a higher aspect ratio, an asset for reducing the tip artifacts.

In many cases, the long tip allows localized imaging of the sample and improves cantilever clearance. Table 1 gives an overview of tip geometries available from several manufacturers. The tip shape and length of an AFM probe can strongly affect image quality. Depending on the sample roughness and the profile of the imaged features, various imaging artifacts may appear and degrade the result. In the worst cases, certain features may not be resolved at all. In general, having a small cone angle is beneficial to reduce convolution with the sample. In most available technologies, the shape of the tip is well defined on 100-300 nm from the tip apex. In Vmicro probes, this angle is constant on several microns from the tip apex.

Manufacturer	Model	Tip shape	Tip height	Tip cone half angles	Source
Bruker	SCANASYST-AIR	4-sided pyramidal	2.5-8 μm	17.5-25°	https://www.brukerafmprobes.com/p-3726-scanasyst-air.aspx
Nanosensors	PPP-NCHR	4-sided pyramidal	7-15 μm	20-30°	https://www.nanoandmore.com/AFM-Probe-PPP-NCHR
BudgetSensors	Tap300	4-sided pyramidal (rotated)	15-19 μm	20-30°	https://www.nanoandmore.com/AFM-Probe-Tap300AI-G
MikroMasch	OPUS160AC	3-sided pyramidal	12-16 μm	0-35°	https://www.opustips.com/AFM-Tip-160AC-NN
Nanoworld	ARROW-NCR	3-sided pyramidal	10-15 μm	20-35°	https://www.nanoandmore.com/AFM-Probe-ARROW-NCR
Nanosensors	ATEC-NC	3-sided pyramidal, tip view	15-20 μm	8-12°	https://www.nanoandmore.com/AFM-Probe-ATEC-NC
AppNano	FORTA	3-sided pyramidal	10-16 μm	20-30°	https://www.appnano.com/spm-probe-catalog
AppNano	ACCESS-NC	3-sided pyramidal	14-16 μm	10-20°	https://www.appnano.com/spm-probe-catalog
Nunano	SCOUT-350	Conical	10-13 μm	25°	https://www.nunano.com/store/scout-350
Vmicro	Lprobe® series	3-sided pyramidal, tip view	30-40 μm	7-8°	www.vmicroafmprobes.com and this paper
Vmicro	XLprobe® series	3-sided pyramidal, tip view	100-110 μm	7-8°	www.vmicroafmprobes.com and this paper

Table 1: AFM probes produced using batch microfabrication process on silicon wafers: technical specifications based on commercial public data

4) Operation in Liquids

When AFM is operated in liquids, a well-known occurring phenomenon is the hydrodynamic squeeze-film force between the cantilever and surface[6], that reduces the cantilever frequency, its quality factor Q and the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). Increasing lever–surface spacing with longer tips not only eases imaging highly corrugated samples in liquids such as cells or tissues, but reduces this damping. This maintains the cantilever frequency to its nominal value in liquid whatever the tip–surface distance. Benefits are expected in all imaging modes. In particular, for imaging based on non-resonant modes, the cantilever bandwidth is preserved whatever the distance to surface.

5) Electrical Modes

Electrical modes cover a large family of techniques implemented in AFM microscopes. They aim at measuring and imaging local electrical information concurrently with the sample topography. Typically, the electrical potentials of the tip and the sample are actively controlled. For this reason, tips used in these techniques are preferably covered by a thin conductive coating. The first electrical mode that was invented is the conductive AFM (C-AFM) [7]. In this mode, the tip is in contact with the sample and acts as an electrode. A bias voltage is applied between the tip and the sample; the resulting current is measured, and the local conductivity is recorded simultaneously with the topography.

FIG. 5: Interest of using long tip probes for KPFM measurements

Local potentials can be measured in tapping or non-contact operation, using for example two main techniques named Electrostatic Force Microscopy (EFM) and Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy (KPFM) [8, 9]. FIG. 5 shows typical setups. EFM measures the electrostatic force between the probe and the sample. Because electrostatic forces act over long distances, the tip is typically lifted by 50–150 nm to suppress sensitivity to short-range van der Waals forces. In KPFM, the probe oscillates in dynamic mode at a frequency f_1 and is kept at constant tip–sample distance by the standard z-feedback loop. While recording the topography, an AC electrical excitation at a frequency f_2 is applied. A second feedback loop controls the mechanically detected response to the AC excitation by adjusting the DC tip bias. Various KPFM schemes can be implemented—Amplitude Modulation (AM-KPFM), Frequency Modulation (FM-KPFM) [10], often leveraging a cantilever harmonic to increase sensitivity. In all electrical modes, the signal originating from the probe originates from three contributions: the tip apex, the tip cone, and the cantilever. If the tip shape is not conical, models often approximate it as an equivalent cone for the shank between the apex and the cantilever. Depending on the mode, the relative contribution of each part varies.

EFM and AM-KPFM are simpler to implement than FM-KPFM, thus they remain attractive techniques for mapping electrostatic properties at the nanoscale. However, their performance is often limited by parasitic contributions that affect spatial resolution and quantitative accuracy. A limitation arises from the cantilever, which can contribute up to 80 % of the total electrostatic signal [11]. Unlike the tip apex and the tip cone, the cantilever is not located directly above the interaction area. Its large capacitive coupling with the sample increases the overall capacitance gradient dC/dz , leading to parasitic electrostatic forces that blur the image and degrade the resolution. Vmicro addresses this limitation with the Lprobes[®] and the XLprobes[®], featuring tips that are 3 to 25 times longer than those of conventional AFM probes. These geometries drastically reduce the cantilever-sample capacitance and consequently the associated dC/dz . The parasitic electrostatic forces between the cantilever and the sample are reduced by a factor of 9–225.

FIG. 6: Interest of using long tip probes for PFM measurements

Piezoresponse Force Microscopy (FIG. 6) is another useful technique that aims at imaging or changing piezoelectric and ferroelectric material at the nanoscale. The technique is very powerful to image domains with different polarization orientation. However, artifacts can occur that can be related to cantilever bending or torsion [12], and/or strong influence of electrostatic forces on the cantilever itself. Here, using high aspect ratio tips is considered to be a better approach [13],[14]. In this context, Vmicro probes will offer both a long tip and the reproducible specifications regarding the apex and the mechanical behavior of the cantilever. In all the electrical modes of the AFM, using cantilevers with long tips will reduce the DC electrostatic force seen by the cantilever.

6) Optical Modes

Several near-field techniques using optical sources combined to an AFM setup enable to measure optical properties of the sample at resolutions below the diffraction limit known with far field optical systems. In the last 20 years, a few configurations have gained strong interest since they enable to assess chemical properties at the nanoscale using previously known spectroscopy databases and achievements. Scattering Scanning Near Field Optical Microscope (s-SNOM), shown in FIG. 7, has widespread in the apertureless configuration, that is based on illuminating the tip-surface region with a laser, collecting and analyzing the light scattered by the tip [15],[16]. It has been predicted and observed that antenna effects can enhance the signal [17], however the solutions that imply

tailoring the tip with focused ion beam methods are not scalable with affordable probe costs when the aim is addressing the whole users community. For operation in IR to mid IR wavelengths, metal coated tips of 8 to 15 microns issued from electrical modes products ranges can be used. However, for s-SNOM operation at long wavelengths in mid-IR to THz, such tips lack of efficiency for delivering the signal because they are too small compared to wavelengths [18], calling for probes having several tens of microns and possibly above 100 μm lengths.

FIG. 7: impact of the tip geometry on scattering SNOM technique. (a) small tips ($8\mu\text{m}$ - $15\mu\text{m}$) introduce a wavelength cutoff and are efficient only in IR range. (b) higher tip lengths unlock the antenna transfer function and thus enable to extend the imaging and spectroscopic studies to far IR and THz wavelengths

Vmicro in plane technology enables to produce batch processing of probes with 40 μm to 100 μm tip lengths (FIG. 7 (b)) that are compatible with IR SNOM and that have demonstrated successful THz imaging in the SNOM configuration[19-22]. Another established optical near field technique is AFM-IR. Its principle is based on illuminating the sample and recording with an AFM tip the expansion induced by light absorption[23]-[24]. This technique has enabled various studies on polymers, bio-samples, semiconductors[25]. In some situations, the sample expansion around the tip can be acoustically coupled to the cantilever [26]. In configurations depending on the surface reflectivity and the materials present on tip and cantilevers, light incoming on the probe can generate a perturbative signal or long-term drifts. These drifts can also originate from the presence of several thermal expansion coefficients when incoming light transfers heat. This can happen when a metal coating is deposited onto silicon or silicon nitride.

FIG. 8: AFM-IR technique and improvements offered by high lengths tips. (a) small tips result in having the cantilever close to the surface that emits acoustic power under the photothermal effect and produces unwanted signal superimposed to the signal sensed by the tip. (b) Higher tip length results in taking the cantilever away from the acoustic sources, leading to reduced coupling.

FIG. 8 shows two configurations with standard tips (a) and high length tips (b). In (b), assuming a distance increase by a factor of 12 and an inverse squared power dependence, we expect that the acoustic power reaching the cantilever should be divided by two orders of magnitudes as compared to (a). Using Vmicro high length tips, such a parasitic signal is expected to couple with orders of magnitude less. Moreover, in FIG. 8 (b) when getting the cantilever far from the surface the incoming laser beam and the light resulting from surface diffusion will impact less the cantilever.

7) Conclusion

The long tip probe designs enabled by Vmicro technology are only at the beginning of a new chapter in AFM history. In further AFM multiphysical measurements that implement mechanical with electrical modes and/or optical modes, it is also expected that long probes will be a key asset.

8) Contact and information

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9) References

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